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INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS

Coordinator

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ISS **BioSense**
Innovation in Optical Biosensors

www.swinostics.eu

SWINOSTICS

SWine diseases field diag**NOSTICS** toolbox

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771649

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THE SENSOR - TECHNOLOGY

SWINOSTICS sensors have been developed based on bio-photonic sensing technology.

The main sensing chip is attached to the photonic circuit by means of a fiber array, which makes it simple for the use to replace the sensor. The first sensors ready for lab validation have been delivered.

THE SENSOR - BIOLOGY

The SWINOSTICS biosensors exploit antibodies and are able to detect six important viruses for the swine industry (ASFV, PRRSV, SIV, PPV PCV2, CSF).

LAB TESTING

First laboratory tests have been performed with good results. Next test for full system validation are expected in early 2020.

DEVICE & FLUIDICS

The sensor microfluidics and overall SWINOSTICS device fluidics allow operating the device in the field/point of care. The first prototype is being validated.

SOFTWARE INTERFACE

The device is controlled through an Android App. A web platform is also available for extended functionalities and further data analysis.

PUBLICATIONS

